

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMORU****FIRST NAME: PAUL****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. How to Write a Good Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021,7-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2012, 43-57)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1) INTRODUCTION

I have been deeply enthused and enlightened by the rich and empowering content while interacting with the ACA-401D course pack (Period 1). The rich content exposed me to the general overview of the basics of academic essay writing, elaborated steps for writing a good essay, and most importantly, the key rule of thumb for writing a paper. These foundational concepts also covered areas like American vs British English, Plagiarism, Style Guide, CMS Crib Sheet, and Latin Abbreviations and Expressions. The above seven concepts, as learned from the ACA-401D course pack is what my response paper will be premised on.

2) **HOW TO WRITE A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY**

The ACA-401D period one, the course pack, and the short video tutorial enriched my understanding of the ingredients for a good academic essay/paper and the protocols acceptable by Euclid University. What sets apart academic or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing, which includes materials published in journals, books, newspapers, and conference papers. Academic writing is presented in three (3) parts: the introduction, body, and conclusion. To fulfill the requirement of being nonfictional, academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations, and references to other works. In a nutshell, academic writings provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2021, 7-14). I have therefore been taken through what it takes to start an academic essay, researching the topic, organising my ideas, the actual writing of an academic essay and referencing the essay. Other critical steps include editing the essay, handing in the essay, and up to eight (8) ideas under rules of thumb for academic paper.

3) **PUNCTUATIONS**

Concept three (3) has been very exciting for me. I encountered many new rules and scenarios for appropriate use of punctuations. Based on my personal experience, I am tempted to claim that use of appropriate punctuations is probably one of the least understood aspects of writing, especially when it comes to academic writing. It is also very technical, though personally until I started this course, I had never taken or even understood deeply how and when to apply punctuation marks, their meaning, their types and the differences between correct and incorrect use of punctuation marks. The general rule that stood out for me was to use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence. Equally, the use of apostrophe, brackets, colon and semicolon stood out for me and I now appreciate their meaning, context and application.

4) **AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH**

Over the years, I have mindlessly used the standard American English (SAE) and the standard British English (SBE) interchangeably, even in one body of text. Indeed the two are more similar than different, especially with “educated” or “scientific” English. (EUCLID 2021, 25.) But after interacting with this EUCLID content, I have grown more sensitive about the additional meaning they convey when it comes to grammar, syntax, punctuations and general usage. Sometimes the same words convey different or additional meaning. On this premise, the greatest take home for me is that SAE and SBE should never be used interchangeably while writing academic papers at EUCLID. A clear call for consistency has been made and this will significantly influence my work and writing throughout this course and thereafter.

5) **PLAGIARISM**

Under this concept of plagiarism, what stood out for me this that the mark of honour for any scholar or academic endeavour is originality and attribution or acknowledgment of the works of other authors whenever their ideas are relied upon when generating new or additional body of knowledge. This course has offered me a deeper understanding of plagiarism and how to avoid it. I have also gained an understanding of how and when to cite and paraphrase when writing an academic paper and to insert footnotes using MS Word. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34).

6) **STYLE GUIDE**

It is awesome to be right at the beginning of this exciting academic journey to be guided on the style to use as a scholar. Connected to this is the importance for a writer to appreciate the reasons or purpose why a particular style should be used and what a style guide constitutes. I have learnt that EUCLID prefers Chicago Rules (Turabian), even though other internationally recognised rules are also accepted. According to EUCLID (2021, 41), a style is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In all of these cases, there is need to maintain consistency. Whereas there is no single authoritative source on style for writing English, choosing one like it is recommended by EUCLID encompasses aspects like: preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, spelling (UK Vs US for example), use of symbols among others. In a nutshell, a scholar interested in being published will critically benefit from the use of a style guide and have his or her academic work respected and recognised.

7) **CMS CRIB SHEET**

Chapter SIX of the course pack deeply enriched my understanding of the Chicago Style and specifications of Chicago Style and offered typical examples of the same. Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press) EUCLID (2021, 44). The usage of the Chicago Style guided me on the appropriate tools and literary resources significant in aiding the writing of my academic papers, including what dictionaries to use. This makes life easy and demystifies the complexities of writing a scholarly piece of work. This will immensely support my work and contribution to advancing the frontier of knowledge as a scholar. Important concepts include using abbreviations, caps or capitalisation, compound words, italics and quotation marks, numbers, and footnotes, among others.

8) CONCLUSION

The conceptual foundation necessary for proficiency in scholarly writings or academic papers has eloquently been addressed by ACA-401D period one course pack. Actually, I now appreciate that academic writing is a discipline that can only be achieved through a methodical and empirical sourcing and presentation of data or information with an objective of advancing the frontier of knowledge while recognising works of previous scholars. Therefore, as I embark on this fulfilling academic journey, this course pack will remain my friend and companion. Certainly, I am grateful and now look confidently to the future and a commitment to continue to study and master the tools, guidelines and concepts covered by this course pack until I am proficient.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.